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Use of Vanadate. Oxidative Decarboxylation of α -Hydroxy Acids

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VANADIUM(V) is a strong oxidising agent in perchloric acid and it has been found to be effective in dilute perchloric acid, hydrochloric acid or acetic acid for the oxidative decarboxylation of α -hydroxycarboxylic acids. Considering the easy availability and stability of the reagent as well as the easy workup procedure and short reaction time, this method appears to be an excellent one and it can compete with other oxidants¹⁻⁹. So the present investigation was undertaken by selecting readily available benzoic acid as the pilot compound to establish the optimum condition of the oxidation.

Thus a mixture of benzoic acid (**1**; X=Y=C₆H₅; 1 mol equivalent) and sodium (or ammonium) metavanadate (2 mol equivalents) in perchloric acid (70%) diluted with equal volume of water was heated under reflux for ten minutes. As the reaction proceeded the reaction mixture assumed a deep-blue colour which remained unchanged till the end of the reaction. The reaction mixture on usual workup furnished benzophenone (**2**; X=Y=C₆H₅) in 80% yield which remained unchanged on extending the refluxing time upto 4 h or substituting perchloric acid by either hydrochloric acid (6 or 1 N) or glacial acetic acid. The reaction failed in the neutral or alkaline medium and use of less than two molar equivalents of vanadate resulted in the low yield of the desired carbonyl compound. The yield of benzophenone also remained unaltered by employing dimethylsulphoxide or dimethylformamide as solvent or by stirring the reaction mixture at room temperature (25–30 min), but with 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene, it was necessary to heat the reaction mixture under reflux temperature for at least

10 min. Mandelic acid on similar oxidation did not furnish benzylformic acid; only 15% of benzaldehyde and a trace of benzoic acid were obtained.

Oxidation of aliphatic α -hydroxycarboxylic acids, like citric, tartaric, glycollic, malic and lactic, by similar treatment with vanadium(V) in dilute perchloric acid medium furnished the desired carbonyl compounds (in 10–15% yield) which were isolated from the reaction mixtures through distillation. They were identified through the formation and purification (chromatography over alumina) of the corresponding 2,4-DNP derivatives and m.m.p. determination of the latter with the respective authentic samples. From these experiments it became evident that with aliphatic substrates the present method was unsuitable.

Experimental

Oxidation of benzoic acid (1; X=Y=C₆H₅): To a mixture of benzoic acid (0.6 g) in perchloric acid (70%; 10 ml) and water (10 ml) was added sodium (or ammonium) metavanadate (0.7 or 0.6 g, respectively) and the reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 10 min under inert atmosphere. The clear deep-blue reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water (20 ml) and extracted (3 × 50 ml) with a mixture of ether and benzene (1 : 1, v/v). The organic layer was washed successively with water (1 × 20 ml), caustic soda (1 N; 20 ml; preserved) and water (3 × 20 ml), then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvent a colourless oily residue (0.5 g) was obtained which furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 235°, which remained undepressed on admixture with the 2,4-DNP derivative of benzophenone¹⁰. The crude ketone was purified by evaporative distillation at 165–70°/6 mm to furnish colourless crystals (0.4 g; 80%), m.p. 46°, which remained undepressed on admixture with benzophenone. The ir spectra (Perkin–Elmer 297 infrared grating spectrophotometer) of the product and that of the authentic benzophenone were identical in all respect, ν_{max} (nujol), 1980, 1925, 1800, 1640, 1595, 1575, 1445, 1320, 1275, 1175, 1150, 1075, 1030, 1000, 995, 945, 935, 915, 820, 765, 705, 695 and 640 cm⁻¹. Unreacted benzoic acid could not be recovered from the alkaline extract through usual workup.

Oxidation of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene: A mixture of 9-carboxy-9-hydroxyfluorene (0.6 g), ammonium metavanadate (0.6 g), perchloric acid (70%; 10 ml) and water (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 10 min. The light green reaction mixture was cooled. On workup in the aforementioned method it furnished a neutral product (0.4 g) which was purified by evaporative distillation at 160–65°/6–7 mm when pure fluorenone was obtained as pale yellow needles (0.3 g, 60%), m.p. 81°, m.m.p. with authentic fluorenone remained undepressed. However, fluorenone was obtained in quantitative yield by heating the reaction mixture for 2 h. The product furnished a 2,4-DNP derivative, m.p. 280–83° (lit.¹¹ 283°). The ir spectra of

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the product and that of the authentic fluorenone were identical in all respect, $\nu_{\max}$ (nujol), 1 950, 1 925, 1 830, 1 715, 1 610, 1 595, 1 445, 1 370, 1 295, 1 195, 1 095, 1 080, 950, 915, 880, 810, 780, 730, 665 and 645 cm^{-1} .

Oxidation of mandelic acid: A mixture of mandelic acid (1.5 g), ammonium metavanadate (2.4 g), perchloric acid (20 ml) and water (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 10 min. The deep blue reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene (1 : 1, v/v; 3×50 ml). The organic layer was extracted with sodium hydroxide solution (1 N; 20 ml; preserved), washed with water (2×25 ml) and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On removal of the solvents an oily residue (trace) was obtained which furnished the 2,4-DNP derivative of benzaldehyde, m.p. 235–37°. It corresponded to 15% formation of benzaldehyde in the reaction.

The aforementioned alkaline extract was acidified (congo red) with concentrated hydrochloric acid and extracted with ether (3×25 ml). The organic layer was washed with a little water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue (0.5 g), obtained after removal of the solvent, was crystallised from water to furnish benzoic acid (0.4 g), m.p. 121°, m.m.p. with authentic benzoic acid remained undepressed.

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Isomerisation of Double Bond in Nitrosteroids

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MITIU¹ and Jones² reported the conversion of 6-nitro-5-ene to the corresponding 6 β -nitro-4-ene in the cholestane series by using methanolic solution of KOH in 6 days. In this paper we want to report a quick, convenient and versatile method for the transformation of readily available 6-nitrocholest-5-enes (1–4) to 6 β -nitrocholest-4-enes (5–7) in excellent yield.

- 1, R=H
- 2, R=Cl
- 3, R=OAc
- 4, R=OH

- 5, R=H
- 6, R=OCH₃
- 7, R=OH
- 8, R=OAc

6-Nitrocholest-5-ene (1)³ and its 3 β -chloro (2)⁴, 3 β -acetoxy (3)⁵ and 3 β -hydroxy (4)⁶ analogues in acetonitrile when treated with methanolic 5% KOH afforded 6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (5), 3 β -methoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (6) and 3 β -hydroxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (7), respectively. Further acetylation of 7 gave 3 β -acetoxy-6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (8). These nitrosteroids have been characterised on the basis of their spectral data and chemical transformation.

Experimental

All m.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were determined with a Perkin–Elmer 237 spectrophotometer. ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) were run on a Varian A60 instrument with Me₄Si as the internal standard. Tlc plates were coated with silica gel. An aqueous 20% solution of perchloric acid was used as the spraying agent. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

General procedure: The nitroolefin (1; 1.0 g) was dissolved in acetonitrile (25 ml) and methanolic 5% KOH (15 ml) was added. The content was refluxed for 2 h on a water-bath. After completion of reaction, the solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and again with water. The ethereal layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated. The semisolid mass thus obtained was recrystallised from methanol to give 6 β -nitrocholest-4-ene (5; 0.82 g, 82%), m.p. and m.m.p. 112° (lit⁷. 113–15°) (Found: C,